

Space-time Intervals Associated with Momentum and Energy?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 27, 2025

The notion of energy and momentum being directly linked to space-time intervals already exists in Newtonian mechanics in the form of a wave, such as those on strings, in water and sound waves. It is known that higher energy waves (higher frequency) are linked with shorter wavelengths. Thus, E and p can be directly associated with space-time intervals, but in the Newtonian world, this only occurs for waves in a medium. The point seems to be that rest mass may be described by a center-of-mass point in Newtonian mechanics and so E ($KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$) and $p = mv$ may be associated with this point. There is no medium in such a case. In particular, this point based Newtonian mechanics may be applied to the medium which holds the wave, e.g. a string. As a result, a wave seems to be a special E - p object which, although having E and p linked with x - t intervals, is ultimately governed by a medium which is described by Newtonian mechanics of center-of-mass points and E and p being restricted to these points.

If one considers electromagnetism, which deals with charged particles linked with electric and magnetic fields, it seems to go beyond usual Newtonian mechanics, but the center-of-mass point still applies to a charged object and there is the notion of force. A possible issue is the emergence of a photon wave solution (wave-equation in the electric field and a separate one in the magnetic, with $c = \text{speed of light in a vacuum} = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0\mu_0}$). Like waves in media (string, water, air), the speed of light depends on properties of space ϵ_0 , μ_0 and seems to be the same when viewed from different moving frames, which violates Galilean invariance. It seems it was once believed that light moved in a medium, hence making it identical to regular waves in media. We suggest that one does not need a priori medium to account for a photon. In such a case, the electric and magnetic fields create the medium, but are also part of periodic behaviour of the photon in space and time. In other words, one has E, p , periodicity and space and time intervals defined by E and p .

We note that Maxwell's laws of electromagnetism are linked with special relativity. The key issue is that the laws of special relativity for a particle with rest mass, (presumably a Newtonian type particle with a point center-of-mass) necessarily involve the presence of c , the speed of light which acts as an upper bound to speed. This is completely at odds with Newtonian mechanics which has no such limit, we argue. Furthermore, a particle with rest mass has no medium and yet equations written for such a particle: $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m^2c^4$ and $-Et + px = -E't' + p'x'$, also hold for a photon for $m_0 = 0$. In other words, one set of equations (in E, p) holds for both a particle with rest mass and a photon, making it a little difficult to argue that one object, the photon, requires a medium, and the other (particle with rest mass) does not.

What then should one conclude? We first try to show that a constant speed c must be linked with E, p and that these, in turn, are associated with wavelike motion. We then suggest that if one set of equations holds for both photons and particles with rest mass, then the idea of E and p being linked, not with a point, but with intervals of t, x for a photon should carry-over to a particle with rest mass. In other words, one does not restrict E and p to a point for a particle with rest mass, as in Newtonian mechanics. This, we argue, is the idea of free particle quantum mechanics and it has its roots in special relativity.

Newtonian Mechanics and the Concept of a Wave

Newtonian mechanics deals with rest mass objects which may be described by a center-of-mass point. Force is rendered in a tiny dx which tends to zero. Thus, energy ($KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$) and momentum, $p = mv$, seem to be associated with this center-of-mass point. A physical example, called a wave, seems to be a contradiction to this view in that it is periodic (sinusoidal) and involves frequencies and wavelengths associated with E and p . Examples of waves include ones on strings, in water and sound waves in air and other media. In such a case, E and p are directly linked with spatial and time intervals. The “catch” is that such waves require a medium and it is the medium which regulates the speed. Thus, unlike a Newtonian rest mass object, which one may presumably accelerate for ever, always increasing speed, a wave has a fixed speed based on medium parameters and is not linked with a center-of-mass point. Newtonian mechanics, however, may be used to describe the medium (as made of center-of-mass points of particles with rest mass) and so a wave is seen to follow from Newtonian mechanics, even though it violates a number of Newtonian aspects of a particle with rest mass. Thus, in Newtonian mechanics, a wave seems to be a special case object with E, p and $x-t$ intervals linked with E, p as well as a fixed speed linked to medium parameters.

The Photon Wave of Maxwell's Equations

Maxwell's electromagnetic equations allow for the solution of two wave-equations, one for the electric field and the other, for the magnetic:

$$-\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial Field} + \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial Field} = 0 \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}}$$

Given that speed is constant ($c = \text{speed of light in a vacuum}$), it seems one has again a wave in a medium. After all, electromagnetism involves forces and acts on charged particles which have rest mass and a center-of-mass point. Unlike the usual waves (string, water, air), it is not the charged particles which create the medium, however, but the medium seems to be linked to the electric and magnetic fields because ((1)) is obtained by setting all point charges and currents to zero.

The question we ask is: Does one have to assume a medium for a photon? It seems that one does not because it is not Newtonian center-of-mass point particles which create any such medium. The electric and magnetic fields (which are linked to force) and oscillate periodically are the medium, but at the same time are intertwined and define the photon. Thus, one has a constant speed c which is the same as seen by all moving frames because $c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}}$, $x-t$ intervals \hbar/p , \hbar/E , and no medium. One may argue that this is fine, but how does this relate to a particle with rest mass and a center-of-mass point? One may simply argue that there are three different phenomena: a particle with rest mass, a wave in a medium and a photon.

The problem with this scenario seems to lie with the equations of special relativity which, when written in terms of E, p, x, t apply equally well to a particle and a photon.

Special Relativity

Special relativity, i.e. a Lorentz transformation, may be derived for a particle with rest mass to describe how x and t are viewed by a frame moving with $-v$. In particular,

Rest frame: m_0 at rest at $x=0, t$ ((2a)) Moving frame: $x'/t' = v$ ((2b))

In other words, x' and t' cannot be the same in the moving frame because the rest mass object is seen to be moving and one cannot have $x=0, t=0$ and $x=0, t$ as in the rest frame. This leads to:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v/b) & v/b \\ v/b & g(v/b) \end{vmatrix} \quad ((3))$$

The point is that one must introduce a velocity parameter b which is a constant, i.e. the same in all frames. Using $xx-bbtt = x'x' - bbt't'$ one finds that:

$$g(v/b) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb} \quad ((4))$$

Thus, b seems to also be an upper bound on the speed of a particle with rest mass. This violates Newtonian mechanics which suggests that there is no upper bound on speed and that one may continually accelerate a particle. The idea of a constant b seems to be analogous to a wave moving in a medium, but why should there be a wave or medium in a matrix describing a particle with rest mass seen from one frame or another?

One may see that ((3)) not only applies to $x'/t'=v$ (particle with rest mass), but is consistent with:

$$x/t=b \quad \text{and} \quad x'/t' = b \quad ((5))$$

Furthermore, for a particle with rest mass, m_0 and $p=0$ in the rest frame seem to also transform according to ((3)) leading to $E = m_0 c c g(v)$ and $p = m_0 v g(v)$.

At this stage, a particle with a rest mass is still presumably represented by a center-of-mass point and one may argue that it is a peculiarity that b appears in ((3)).

If one assumes that $b=c$, the speed of light in a vacuum, then Maxwell's equations describe the wave-like features of the photon. We consider here the case of not making resort to Maxwell's em equations.

One is then faced with describing b . If this represents a physical entity, then there should be an associated E, p , but b is always constant. This is very similar to a wave in a medium, but the traditional Newtonian view is that rest mass particles create the medium, Here ((3)) and ((5)) show that ((3)) applies both to a particle with rest mass and the b object, which is non-Newtonian. Thus, one transformation applies to both and each has an E, p which is not distinguished. For example, one may consider special relativistic equations such as:

$$E = pc \quad \text{and} \quad -Et + px = -E't' + p'x' \quad ((6))$$

In these equations, one does not distinguish between a rest mass particle (except that $m_0 \neq 0$) and one with $m_0 = 0$ because one cannot increase b .

Let us examine a b speed particle in more detail. First of all, it cannot have a rest mass because otherwise one could have a frame moving faster than $-b$ which would see the object moving faster than b . Given that b is a constant, it seems to be reminiscent of a wave (like a string, water or air wave), but there is no medium. Nevertheless, b should depend on some kind of parameters of space. Furthermore, there must be an E and p linked with b because otherwise there is no meaning to the motion b . This means that:

$$\text{Frame A } x/t = b \quad E, p \quad \text{Frame B } x'/t' = b \quad E', p' \quad ((7))$$

Here the two frames differ by a relative speed of $-v$. B is the same as seen in both, but momentum cannot be because a target in the moving frame brings momentum into a collision. Thus, v must enhance p , i.e. E' and p' transform according to v . Furthermore, x is measured from an origin in frame 1 and the moving frame sees this origin as moving, so it seems that x', t' must also transform due to v . If one assumes the same Lorentz transformation for both (which also applies to a particle with rest mass and its E, p), then:

$$-Et + px = -E't' + p'x' \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is reminiscent of the wave condition: $\text{velocity} = x/t = \text{frequency} \cdot \text{wavelength} \quad ((9))$

This, however, may be a coincidence. We note, however, something important about ((8)).

$$x = bt \quad \text{and} \quad x' = bt' \quad \text{If } -Et + px = 0 \quad \text{then } x/t = p/E \quad \text{for all frames} \quad ((10))$$

$E = pc$ is more than a math relation, we argue. It shows that not only are x and t constrained by c , but so are E and p . E and p are directly linked to motion and one may suggest that they are linked to a kind of self-medium. Given the Newtonian notion of action-reaction, it seems that E and p are linked to forces and the association with ((9)) is more than a coincidence. The point, we argue, is that one may increase E and p , but the system is still constrained to move at c , so somehow E and p are participating in this speed c . One does not have the case of an acceleration which creates E and p and then allows the particle to translate (drift) it seems. If this were the case, it is not clear what would constrain the speed to c .

Thus, for b , it seems that there is an E and p which are linked to the usual Newtonian ideas of energy/heat and impulse hit, but also participate in motion through an association with forces and are linked with frequency and wavelength. This means that interactions do not occur at the center-of-mass point, but are periodic and over length and time intervals. This is in keeping with the Maxwell result for a photon (electric and magnetic fields) and so $b = c$ seems reasonable.

The final issue is to note that the special relativistic equations;

$$-Et+px = -E't' + p'x' \quad \text{and} \quad Ex + pcct = 0 \quad ((11))$$

do not distinguish between the E,p of a particle with rest mass and the b object. Thus, if E and p are linked with:

$$\Delta t = \hbar/E \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta x = \hbar/p \quad ((12))$$

For a $b=c$ particle, this same result should hold for a particle with rest mass. In other words, the idea that E,p are only associated with the center-of-mass point for a particle with rest mass does not seem to hold. One may note that \hbar was explicitly obtained by Planck for a photon and not a particle with rest mass. In such a case, the constant speed c must appear because it is the value which applies to a particle with no rest mass. In the case of a particle with rest mass, there must also be an association with c , which there is, because one cannot write a Lorentz transformation for x,t , but must use x, ct . One cannot use vt , because v is part of the Lorentz matrix, i.e. the transformation. Thus, one has a close association between a photon and particle with rest mass when equations are written in terms of E,p.

We suggest that ((12)) applying to both a photon and particle with rest mass means 2-slit interference occurs for both and one essentially has free particle quantum mechanics arising from special relativity, largely because the theory must handle a particle with rest mass and one without in the same equations (written in terms of E and p).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Newtonian mechanics considers a particle with rest mass as being represented by a center-of-mass point, meaning the $KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and $p = mv$ also exist at this same point. At the same, Newtonian mechanics allows for a sinusoidal wave in a medium.. This wave has an energy and momentum p which are associated with space and time intervals, and so there is no a priori center-of-mass picture for a wave. This issue is resolved in Newtonian mechanics by pointing out that the medium consists of Newtonian particles, each of which has a center-of-mass point. Thus, a wave is a “new creation” based on center-of-mass point particles.

Maxwell's equations for a photon, however, lead to two wave-equations, one for the electric field and the other for the magnetic, even though em theory may be described in terms of forces, giving the impression that it is Newtonian. There is no medium for a photon, but there is a fixed speed c for light and an energy and momentum linked to the electric and magnetic fields. One has oscillating force fields associated with energy and momentum, a kind of self-medium we argue, and a period of \hbar/E and wavelength of \hbar/p . This, however, only holds for a photon which, like a wave in a medium, may be called a special object. Thus, so far one has Newtonian center-of-mass points with E and p pertaining to the point and special objects which allow for a time and spatial interval linked with E,p.

We suggest that a major change in viewpoint occurs for special relativistic equations written in terms of E,p, x,t and the Lorentz transformation. The Lorentz transformation holds for both

x, ct and E, pc and for a particle with rest mass and without. One cannot classify the photon as a special object separate from a particle with rest mass in: $-Et+px = -E't'+p'x'$ and $E^2 - pc^2 = 0$.

In particular, one cannot derive the Lorentz transformation for a particle with rest mass without introducing an upper limit speed b and this contradicts Newtonian mechanics. The object with b cannot have a rest mass, but must have an E and p . Its fixed speed seems to be linked with parameters of space. If one uses $-Et+px = 0$, then $E=pc$ in any frame. The key idea is that E and p seem to be linked/constrained with c because as one adds E , p one can only do so by keeping the speed the same. This is reminiscent of a wave, but there is no medium, so we suggest that E , p must somehow be linked to a self-medium. By Newton's action-reaction principle there must also be forces here, so the idea of an oscillating object in x, t with $-Et+px$ being equivalent to $-wt+kx$, means that interactions do not occur at a point, but over a wavelength and period. If special relativistic equations written in terms of E, p, x, t apply to both a particle with rest mass and without, it seems that this non-center-of-mass point type of interaction or period = \hbar/E , wavelength = \hbar/p should apply to particle with rest mass as well. We suggest that this departure from Newtonian mechanics is the root of free particle quantum mechanics, (although there are many more features of quantum mechanics than this, e.g. spin etc.)